

Investigating the Ageing-Parkinson's Disease Nexus: Standardisation of *In Vitro* Models and Techniques by the PD-AGE network

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Introduction

Parkinson's Disease epidemiology

Parkinson's disease (PD) affects 0.3% of the global population, 1% of the over 60s and 5% of the over 80s population – this reflects the fact that ageing is the chief risk factor of PD[1, 2]. PD is best characterised by its motor symptoms: a resting tremor, postural instability, rigidity and bradykinesia; resulting from the neurodegeneration of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc)[3]. Non-motor symptoms, which are less well characterised, include: impaired REM sleep, cognitive dysfunction, depression and anxiety and are more associated with neurodegeneration of non-dopaminergic neuronal populations[4, 5]. A main pathological hallmark of PD is the aggregation of misfolded α -

synuclein, which is incorporated within Lewy Body structures. Lewy Body formation originates within the brainstem and the spread of Lewy Bodies to other brain regions corresponds with disease progression or advanced Braak stage[6]. The exact role of Lewy bodies in contributing to, or otherwise ameliorating, PD pathogenesis caused by toxic soluble α -synuclein (α Syn) species, remains unresolved[7]. DA neurons are the most affected neuronal population in PD but progressive loss of this subtype in the SNpc is also shown to occur in normal ageing[8-13]. This age-associated decline in DA neurons has been shown by a reduction in tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) staining in the SNpc of healthy, aged non-human primates[1, 14]. This also suggests that though there are shared mechanisms of neurodegeneration, particularly of DA neurons in PD and ageing, they appear to be more pronounced in PD[7, 15],

Parkinson's Disease and ageing

There are multiple shared mechanisms in ageing and the pathogenesis of PD, including dysregulated autophagy, genomic instability, telomere attrition, impaired proteostasis, senescence, epigenetic modulation, inflammation, impaired intercellular communication, nutrient sensing, microbiota and mitochondrial dysfunction[16]. Of these mechanisms, mitochondrial dysfunction, dysregulated proteostasis, inflammation and cellular senescence show the greatest degree of overlap between PD and ageing[15]. However, the molecular intricacies underlying these two distinct processes remains unclear.

Mitochondrial dysfunction in PD is linked to reduced electron transport chain complex I activity, first characterised through the selective uptake of MPTP metabolite (MPP⁺) into DA neurons, causing parkinsonism and neuron death[17]. Complex I deficiency has been observed in PD patient nigral tissue homogenate[18] and PD patient-derived fibroblasts[19, 20]. Mitochondrial dysfunction is also implicated in PD through an increase of somatic mtDNA deletions[21] and point mutations[22], in the SNpc of PD patients, resulting in impaired oxidative phosphorylation. MtDNA deletions are also characteristic of pathological ageing within highly metabolic cells such as skeletal muscle fibres[23] and different neuronal populations but especially in SNpc DA neurons[24]. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are implicated in mtDNA deletion formation. DA neurons are at a higher risk to develop oxidative stress associated damage, because ROS are generated through oxidative phosphorylation and through DA metabolism[25].

The combination of mitochondrial dysfunction, elevated ROS, and proteotoxicity, associated with overloaded protein degradation systems, are drivers of inflammation in PD and ageing[26]. Chronic inflammation, termed “inflammaging”, is another hallmark of ageing and neurodegeneration. Chronic inflammation is triggered by damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), such as ROS, ATP and extracellular mtDNA, and results in the production of constitutive, low-level cytokines and further oxidative species which directly damage cells and tissues[27]. Inflammatory markers, such as IL-6 and IL-8, also contribute to the senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP) which leads to the induction of cellular

senescence[28, 29]. Cells with a higher metabolic threshold, such as DA neurons, are most susceptible to chronic inflammation and DA neurons are particularly prone to induced senescence[30].

Senescence in mitotic cells is associated with irreversible cell cycle arrest in response to oncogenic stressors such as DNA damage[31, 32], telomere shortening[33] and epigenetic perturbations[34]. Senescence is initiated by p16 or p21 cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors, which trigger cell cycle arrest in response to the DNA damage response or telomere attrition[35, 36]. Though the mechanistic basis of senescence is less well defined in neurons, relative to mitotic cells, a senescent phenotype has been reported in post-mitotic mouse primary Purkinje neurons through p21-mediated senescent phenotype in response to DNA damage and pro-inflammatory factors[37, 38]. This has, to date, not been investigated in DA neurons. Whilst p16 levels have been shown to be elevated in PD[26] and some studies have suggested telomere attrition is predictive of PD progression and severity[39, 40], contradictory data and lack of consensus on the role of telomere length in PD aetiology, limits the use of telomere length as a robust biomarker of PD and PD pathology in the context of ageing[41-43]. SASP comprises a number of factors that contribute to the senescent phenotype at the cellular level, these include growth factors, chemokines and cytokines, the latter of which can also act in paracrine fashion spreading senescence to neighbouring cells[28]. The senescent phenotype is also characterised by mitochondrial-dependent ROS generation[44], the accumulation of senescence-associated beta-galactosidase (SA- β -gal) in the lysosomes of senescent cells[45, 46], senescence-associated heterochromatic foci (SAHF)[47] and phosphorylation of the histone protein H2AX (γ H2AX) in response to double-stranded DNA breaks[48]. Biomarkers associated with senescence such as SA- β -gal activation, SASP induction, loss of lamin B1, γ H2AX foci and oxidative stress have been observed in aged[30, 38, 44, 49-54] and paraquat-induced parkinsonian mouse models[26]. SA- β -gal and SASP biomarkers have also been observed in rat[55-58] and non-human primate models of ageing[59, 60].

Whilst there is clear evidence supporting the association between PD and ageing, there are notable differences in reported neurochemical and morphological changes in DA neurons in Parkinsonian and aged individuals. These include: the number of stained neurons and immunohistochemical staining of oxidative species, Lewy body inclusions, α Syn aggregation, microglial activation, proteasomal and lysosomal function. This suggests that the interaction between ageing and PD pathophysiology is complex and not fully understood[1, 61]. To better understand common and distinct mechanisms between ageing and PD, it is necessary to be able to standardise the way in which we conduct research in both the fields of ageing and neurodegeneration. This includes recognising the most appropriate disease model(s) and selecting an appropriate panel of biomarkers to best investigate common pathways.

Cellular models of PD and Ageing

Whilst animal models have, and continue to be, an important tool in understanding the mechanistic basis of ageing and PD, a key limitation of animal models is that PD is a uniquely human disease. This may also be true of other diseases but an additional layer of complexity exists when considering the interplay between ageing in the pathogenesis of PD, which itself exists as disparate processes in different species[62]. The time taken for features of PD to manifest, necessitates the use of exogenous induction of certain aspects of PD pathophysiology in animal models[63-67] and no animal can adequately model all facets of PD simultaneously[62]. Cells sampled from patient peripheral tissues, such as PBMCs isolated from blood, allow a more discrete means to assay human tissue biomarkers but data has so far had limited reproducibility[68, 69]. Fibroblasts can also be cultured from patients and age-matched donors and retain some age-associated characteristics, although many features of the PD pathophysiology are less pronounced or not expressed in fibroblasts compared to neurons[19, 70-72]. Features of PD pathology that have been successfully modelled in fibroblasts include mitochondrial dysfunction and turnover[20, 73-78], lysosomal dysfunction[19, 79-83] and inflammation[15, 29, 84].

The discovery and use of “Yamanaka” transcription factors to convert human fibroblasts into human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs), which can then be differentiated into neurons, provides a means to model PD and age-associated disease in a human-based system[85-88]. Since then, a number of cell reprogramming strategies have become available for the conversion of human fibroblasts into neural cells: the differentiation of reprogrammed hiPSCs, the differentiation of reprogrammed induced neuronal progenitor cells (iNPCs)[89, 90] and finally direct reprogramming from fibroblasts into neurons[91-93] and astrocytes[94].

Small molecule factors can be used to differentiate hiPSCs without the use of viral transduction[95]. Dual inhibition of the TGF- β /SMAD pathway using Noggin and SB431542 promotes the differentiation of hiPSCs into a midbrain phenotype and subsequent treatment with Sonic Hedgehog and FGF8b results in differentiation into DA neurons, which express pan-neuronal markers such as β III-tubulin and the DA machinery including the marker TH[96, 97]. Subsequently, a range of hiPSC derived neuronal models of idiopathic and familial PD, have been derived from patient somatic cells such as fibroblasts - including from patients harbouring *SNCA*, *PINK1*, *PRKN*, *LRRK2* and *GBA* mutations[70, 86, 98-111], as well as sporadic cases[87, 105]. A next step after the development of neuronal models were brain organoids, where midbrain organoids are of particular relevance for PD. Many midbrain organoid models recapitulating features of PD have been reported[112-117]. More recently, the level of complexity of 3D models have improved, with assembling of midbrain and striatal organoids to mimic the nigrostriatal pathway, as well as with the experimental induction of cellular aging[118].

A notable consequence of the reprogramming process into pluripotency is the loss of cellular ageing signatures, including age-associated changes in DNA methylation patterns and histone modifications, and telomere shortening, which can affect the suitability of this approach in

modelling certain aspects of cellular ageing and neurodegenerative diseases[119, 120]. Other key age-associated features that are lost during rejuvenation are the progressive impairment in oxidative phosphorylation[121], and the age-associated impairment in autophagy[122]. Several studies have highlighted epigenetic regulation of key PD-genes as contributory to the onset and progression of PD[123, 124]. To overcome this limitation, researchers have developed several strategies to induce features of ageing in iPSC-derived cells. These include: long-term culturing[123] and induced telomere shortening[125].

By directly reprogramming terminally differentiated cells directly into somatic cells of another tissue using, for instance, the forced expression of transcription factors, it is possible to circumvent the pluripotency stage[91-93], a methodology termed 'direct cell reprogramming'. Lineage-determining transcription factors can also be used to reprogram somatic cells into subtype-specific neurons, including DA neurons[102, 122, 126].

The use of Yamanaka factors supplemented with neural transcription factors, can be used to reprogram somatic cells into tri-potent induced neural progenitor cells (iNPCs) – which can be differentiated into neurons, astrocytes or oligodendrocytes[89, 90]. This process of 'semi-direct reprogramming' differs from 'direct reprogramming' because somatic cells are first differentiated into progenitor cells, bypassing pluripotency, before being terminally differentiated into cells of a different lineage. This introduces an intermediate step in the differentiation process with the possibility of cryopreserving progenitor cells. This also allows the differentiation of multiple cell types from the same progenitor cells rather than directly reprogramming each cell type individually[90]. The differentiation of human fibroblast-derived iNPCs into iDAs, has been demonstrated for the investigation of metabolic and mitochondrial dysfunction in Parkinson's disease[19, 127, 128]. Successful differentiation of iNPCs into DA neurons has been validated through immunocytochemical staining of neuronal (β III-tubulin, MAP2 and NeuN) and DA markers (TH and dopamine transporter, DAT;[128]). Importantly, in dermal fibroblasts, there exists an endogenous somatic mosaicism [129], which can lead to issues related to the clonal nature of iPSCs, which is not the case when using direct and semi-direct reprogramming. However, inherent inter-individual variability can impact the yield and reprogramming efficiency of directly reprogrammed cells[122, 130, 131], or result in phenotypically immature neurons[132]. Overall, directly or semi directly reprogrammed cells are less characterised than iPSC derived cells.

The PD-Age Network

The PD-Age network fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers investigating the role of ageing in PD. Working group 2 focused specifically on cell models of ageing and aimed to establish best practices for incorporating ageing into patient-derived cellular models used for PD research. This was done via workshops, questionnaires and literature reviews, to reach consensus on the most appropriate cellular reprogramming models and biomarkers for investigating both ageing and PD. Several measurable biomarkers

have been observed in cellular models of PD and ageing, which can largely be categorised as either inflammatory[133], metabolic[134], (multi)omic[135] or senescent[136]. This selection of biomarker categories is not exhaustive but does reflect a representative cross-section of biomarkers that are compatible with commonly available methodologies, are common to both PD and ageing and align with the collective expertise of the working group members for the purpose of deciding the suitability, practicability and ease of adoption of these different biomarkers. Here, we document the outputs from these sessions, made up of a panel of researchers with expertise in ageing and PD, to facilitate the standardisation of methodologies for the benefit of researchers of all experience levels wishing to conduct research into the impact of ageing on PD progression.

Choosing Cell Reprogramming Route

iPSCs as a versatile tool for modelling neurodegenerative diseases

iPSCs have revolutionised disease modelling by offering a virtually limitless source of human cells with the potential to differentiate into any cell type of interest. To date, many protocols have been established to differentiate iPSCs into various cell types of the brain, utilising developmental signalling cues—such as proteins, small molecules, and transcription factors—that are active during embryonic development. Because these developmental routes have been extensively characterised, designing new differentiation protocols is generally more straightforward compared to direct reprogramming methods. Additionally, since these protocols mimic natural developmental trajectories, cells differentiated from iPSCs typically resemble primary cell types more closely than those that are directly reprogrammed from fibroblasts. Due to their pluripotent nature, iPSCs can be expanded *in vitro* prior to differentiation, thus resulting in a high yield of both pluripotent and differentiated cells, and the possibility to scale-up experiments to perform large-scale screens, deep phenotyping experiments or large-scale omics-related studies. As a direct consequence, iPSCs have been characterised in detail, and in some instances, their differentiation paths have been better described than the corresponding processes that control direct reprogramming. Therefore, iPSCs constitute the method of choice when setting up co-culture experiments[137, 138], microfluidic-based organ-on-a-chip cultures[139-145] and 3D cultures[146-150]. The advent of efficient gene editing methods expanded iPSC's versatility, allowing the generation of genetically modified cell lines carrying known pathological mutations or risk variants or correcting such mutations in patient-derived iPSCs, to produce isogenic control lines[151]. Finally, iPSC-derived precursor cells show great structural and functional integration when engrafted, and have been used in clinical trials, further consolidating their biological and translational relevance[152-156].

Induction of cellular ageing in iPSC-derived cells: where do we stand

Among the discussed strategies, we identified the administration of small molecules targeting known ageing-related molecular pathways as the most relevant method to induce ageing in iPSC-derived models of PD[157]. This strategy has multiple advantages: it is easy to use and accessible, time- and cost-effective and very versatile, as the used compounds and their dosage can be adapted based on their relevance to the cell type of choice and the disease to be modelled. Furthermore, simultaneously targeting multiple pathways better mimics the effects of ageing on overall cell health, thus providing a lot of features associated with ageing. To date, the most promising treatment is the SLO cocktail, which combines three molecules, SBI-0206965, Lopinavir and O-151, that respectively target autophagy, Lamin A biogenesis and DNA glycosylase and together base excision repair[158, 159]. Defective autophagosomes lead to impaired mitochondrial clearance and increased oxidative stress, whereas DNA glycosylase and Lamin A biosynthesis impairment affect nuclear architecture and lead to DNA damage accumulation. Although it has not yet been tested in DA neurons, the SLO cocktail has been successfully applied to iPSC-derived cortical neurons from healthy controls and ALS patients[157], and human microglia cells[160], suggesting the method has the potential to be used with many other cell types, and to model various neurodegenerative diseases. One of the compounds used in the SLO cocktail, SBI-0206965, is an inhibitor of ULK1, a key component of the lysosomal/autophagy pathway and has shown strong effects even when used as a stand-alone treatment[157]. Using it as a single molecule could be beneficial in cell types that are highly sensitive to DNA damage. However, it would undermine the advantage of simultaneously targeting multiple pathways to more accurately simulate the effects of ageing.

Historically, the most used methods were based on replicative stress[161], ionizing gamma-ray irradiation[162] or ectopic expression of progerin [85], a truncated, pathogenic version of the nuclear lamina protein Lamin A. The accumulation of progerin inside the nucleus directly affects nuclear morphology and DNA integrity and can result in cell death, a signature of ageing that strongly resembles that of AD and other neurodegenerative diseases. Although very efficient, those methods present caveats and limitations that weaken their relevance in the study of brain ageing in neurodegenerative diseases.

More recent studies have identified alternative methods to induce ageing in iPSC-derived models. It has been proposed that genetic inactivation of SATB1[163], a transcriptional regulator whose expression is reduced in DA neurons of PD patients, could be used to investigate the drivers of ageing specifically occurring in PD as opposed to broad ageing phenotype. RNage [164], an RNA-seq-based method to calculate ageing scores, can be used to both validate and compare existing protocols and as a screening tool to identify novel strategies. When used to study gene expression profiles from cells treated with several hundreds of compounds, it showed that a few of them, including Fludarabine, could induce an increased RNage score, and cause typical markers of cellular ageing. Similarly, a CRISPR-based whole genome screening[165] can also be used to identify regulators of ageing. Briefly, a library of gRNA is created to target several genes that are known to be essential in specific

cell types. Then, those genes are screened to identify novel age modifiers that are relevant to the cell type of interest. This approach in iPSC-derived neurons helped identify the neddylation pathway as a potential regulation of ageing in Alzheimer's disease (AD) and could be used to model late-onset phenotypes in PD models. Although promising, these techniques need to be validated in different systems, and further optimization is also required. All methods are summarised in **Table 1**.

Preserving the ageing signature with semi-direct and direct reprogramming

Although our working group established that iPSC-derived models with accelerated ageing should be the system of choice to study the effects of ageing on PD, there are a few instances where preserving the ageing signature of the donor should be preferred. Neurons and astrocytes directly or semi-directly reprogrammed from patient-derived skin fibroblasts maintain the ageing signature of the donor[122, 166-168].

Directly reprogrammed induced neurons (iNs) retain their age-associated epigenetic and transcriptomic signatures, OXPHOS and autophagy impairment[122, 167-170], DNA damage[122, 167] and expression of mature TAU isoforms[122, 171]. A select number of studies using directly or semi-directly reprogrammed iNs have successfully modelled mitochondrial and lysosomal dysfunction associated with ageing or neurodegenerative disease[19, 121, 122, 128, 167, 168, 172, 173].

Being able to replicate the exact ageing profile in a patient-specific manner, these strategies represent a powerful tool to study disease mechanisms in an aging context. However, direct reprogramming methods were not selected as the preferred reprogramming route because of the current challenges associated with the use of those cell reprogramming methods. Since iNs become post-mitotic quite early on in the differentiation process[174], any study necessitating a high neuronal yield requires extensively expanded fibroblasts, which can lead to replicative senescence or metabolic changes in parental cells impacting on the reprogramming efficiency and the generated cell product[175]. However, semi-reprogramming methods effectively overcome yield limitations, enabling the production of large quantities of neurons[128]. Heterogeneity between batches[15, 122] and lack of protocol standardisation are also prominent limitations of these models. A detailed list of advantages and disadvantages of direct- and semi-reprogramming is reported in **Table 2**.

A feature of PD pathology and ageing not successfully modelled by any of the cell reprogramming methods described so far, is the interaction between distinct cell types within the brain. This could potentially be achieved by the co-culture of different reprogrammed cell types but success in this area has thus far been limited[94, 141, 166, 176-179] and obtaining a sufficient, consistent yield of each cell type is likely to be challenging[180].

In conclusion, iPSC-derived models, and direct and semi-direct reprogramming all present advantages and disadvantages (**Figure 1**). While direct and semi-direct reprogramming is

generally more time and cost-effective and presents the clear advantage of retaining the donor ageing signature, iPSC-based models are overall more standardised, high-throughput and versatile. Thus, selecting the appropriate method should be driven by the specific objectives and needs of the study at hand.

Figure 1 - Models of ageing: strengths and weaknesses. Each criteria is defined as follows: time effective, how quickly the method produces the cell type of interest; cost effective, relative expense of the approach; easy to implement, overall complexity of the method; protocol standardization, availability of standard procedures; quality controlled parental cells, ability to maintain high-quality cells without unwanted mutations or inconsistencies, and accessibility of quality control assays; retention of donor epigenetic age, whether the method preserves age related epigenetic modifications; high yield, efficiency of producing a large number of viable cells; compatibility with high throughput screening, assesses if the method can be used for large-scale drug and guide screening and automated testing; compatibility with parallel cell line handling, easiness to process multiple cell lines at the same time; derived cell type identity and functionality, whether the produced cells accurately resemble their in vivo counterpart; versatility, ability to produce a variety of different cell types; compatibility with gene editing, how well the method supports genome editing techniques; availability of patient-derived cell lines, assesses the availability of cell lines derived from human patients, as well as centralised cell banks and depositories; compatibility with rejuvenation studies, whether the method is suited to test strategies to reverse cellular aging.

	Accelerated ageing in iPSC-derived models	Direct reprogramming	Semi-reprogramming
Time effective	-	++	+
Cost effective	-	++	++
Easy to implement	+	-	+
Protocol standardization	+	-	-
Quality controlled parental cells	++	-	-
Retention of donor epigenetic age	---	+++	++
High Yield	+++	-	+++
Compatibility with high throughput screening	+++	-	+++
Compatibility with parallel cell line handling	+	+++	++
Derived cell type: identity functionality	++ ++	- +	 +
Versatility	+++	+	+
Compatibility with gene editing	+++	+	+
Availability of patient-derived cell lines	+	-	-
Compatibility with rejuvenation studies	-	++	+

Table 1 – Methods of age manipulation in iPSC-derived models of PD.

<p>Long-term culture [136]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to implement • Validated in iPSC-derived models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often results in uncontrolled cellular stress <i>in vitro</i> • Insufficient time in culture for development of adult forms of protein (such as Tau) • Not compatible with slow- or non- proliferating cell types
<p>γ-Ray Irradiation [162]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very efficient • Validated in iPSC-derived models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Causes a broad array of consequences, making it difficult to discriminate between primary and secondary effects • Non-homogenous exposure causes heterogeneity of responses • Not physiologically relevant as brain cells only receive low doses of irradiation • Post-mitotic neurons are highly resistant to radiation
<p>Progerin [85]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combined with PD-related mutations, it recapitulates Parkinson's disease phenotypes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lamin A is not strongly expressed in young neurons, thus may not mimic brain-specific signs of aging • Progerin accumulation causes very severe responses • Extent of representation of chronological aging requires further characterisation • Induced ageing and disease phenotypes may be difficult to discriminate
<p>SATB1 downregulation [163]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in dopaminergic neurons in PD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires genetic manipulation • Not easily applicable in other cell types
<p>Fludarabine [164]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in neurons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires validation for PD modelling
<p>Neddylation [165]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tested in PD-specific models (such as LRKK2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires further validation for PD modelling
<p>Small molecules - SLO cocktail [157 & 160]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in multiple modules • Time and cost effective • Easy to implement • Versatile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mostly tested in ALS, further validation needed in PD
<p>Small molecules - SBI-026965 Lysosomal/autophagy pathway inhibition [157]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has been shown to cause the strongest changes in iPSC-derived neurons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects of the small molecule may be difficult to distinguish from PD-specific features

Table 2 – Advantages and disadvantages of direct and semi-direct reprogramming in the study of ageing in PD.

	Direct Reprogramming	Semi-direct Reprogramming
ADVANTAGES	The epigenetic signature mostly maintained	
	More time-efficient than iPSC-based methods	
	Produce a single-cell type with higher fidelity than iPSC-based methods	
	More idiopathic PD fibroblasts available compared to iPSCs	
	Can be used in rejuvenation studies	
	Identifiable and modifiable idiopathic and sporadic PD phenotypes	
	Relevant protocols for studying the interplay between ageing and PD as the iPSC-derived cells lack the age- and disease- specific features	
	Standardisation of methodology may allow researchers from different backgrounds achieve greater success in differentiating disease-specific cell types	
	Bypasses the pluripotency stage, allowing a more direct lineage conversion	Allows bulking and long-term storage of reprogrammed NPCs
	Lower risk of tumorigenesis as cells skip the highly proliferative pluripotent stage	Allows convenient distribution of NPCs with collaborators with easily implemented protocols
DISADVANTAGES	Technically challenging, resulting in smaller yields	
	Lack of standardised protocols, increasing variability between studies - highlights the need for further validation	
	Fibroblasts carrying mosaic somatic mutations may misrepresent the genetic profile of the donors	
	Varying levels of genome instability might affect proliferation and reprogramming efficiency	
	Heterogenous nature of fibroblasts (including factors such as origin and metabolic state) may increase variability	
	Less susceptible to gene editing	
	Fibroblasts from the elderly are often senescent and do not reprogram efficiently	
	Limited to closely related lineages (e.g. mesodermal fibroblasts create mesodermal neurons)	Limited range of cell types which can be generated

Assessing Ageing in Cellular Models

1. Selection and prioritisation of ageing assays:

To comprehensively evaluate assays that can be used to evaluate cellular age in *in vitro* models of PD the working group identified commonly used assays across four key areas: senescence and inflammaging, omics profiling and mitochondrial function. These key areas were prioritised because they have been clearly linked to ageing[16, 181, 182] but, except for mitochondrial function, remain distinct from the aetiology of heritable Parkinson's disease[183]. Subsequently, the collective expertise of the working group members was surveyed to establish a prioritised list of assays that are robust and can be used to validate ageing phenotypes in cellular models. Figure 2 summarises the selected tests and their corresponding functionalities. An exhaustive list of assays considered and the pros and cons of each is provided in Table 3. Please refer to this table if you would like to perform a more in-depth characterisation of any of the key areas.

Figure 2 - Methods and tests for the assessment of ageing.

To further support researchers looking to perform these assays in their own laboratories we have generated a standardised web platform to share protocols (SOPs) for key assays. Standardisation will help ensure consistency and reproducibility across research groups. The web platform can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15056603>[185]

2. Senescence and Inflammaging:

Cellular senescence phenotypes are highly heterogeneous and vary based on both cell type and the senescence-initiating stimulus. As such there is no single assay that can be used to define senescence, rather a combinatorial approach should be used with careful consideration paid to cell type (Figure 2). Notably, neurons require a tailored approach as

they are post-mitotic and therefore it is not appropriate to measure senescence using assays that are directly tied to replication potential. Following discussion by the working group we recommend prioritising SA- β -Gal, γ H2AX and SASP when establishing assays to measure senescence and DNA damage. The group recognised this is not an exhaustive list and can be expanded including senescence markers and DNA damage markers.

Inflammaging is defined as an increase in proinflammatory cytokines as individuals age. Proinflammatory cytokines are also components of SASP. As outlined in Figure 2, key SASP factors have not been well described across neuronal and glial types and further characterisation and validation are necessary. While IL-6, IL-8, and IL-1 β are likely to be relevant, gene expression studies and multiplex cytokine arrays should be used to establish cell type and stimuli-specific profiles, as the SASP of the different cell types of the brain have not been extensively characterised.

3. Omics:

Omics-related technologies represent fast-moving and evolving tools to measure ageing. DNA methylation clocks are the most established ageing clocks and the recently published Universal ageing clock [184] represents an important step forward in using this technology to measure age in cultured cells such as neurons, and glia. We would point researchers wanting to use this tool to the consortia website (<https://clockfoundation.org>) for further information. Rapid progress is also being made to develop transcriptomic, proteomic and metabolomic-based clocks. Researchers should stay updated with evolving technologies and remain open to the limitations and context-specific applications of these omics approaches (See Table 3).

4. Mitochondria in ageing

Mitochondria have critical roles in both ageing and PD. To measure mitochondrial function, it is recommended that the following assays be prioritised by researchers: mtDNA Mutation Detection, Mitochondrial Morphology Analysis, and Mitochondrial Respiration. However, mitochondrial dysfunction is a key pathology in PD and all the suggested assays have also been used to study PD in the absence of age. Therefore, results should be interpreted carefully, and controls included that allow the impact of disease model and age to be distinguished.

Key findings and Future directions

Age is the single most important risk factor for PD, but the complexity of the interplay between ageing and PD is yet to be fully determined. The various available *in vitro* models for investigation of the link between ageing and this neurodegenerative disease provide a distinct set of advantages and disadvantages. By discussing these properties, the PD-Age network aims to highlight the current variability within those methods, thus the necessity for strict guidelines in the chosen procedures.

We identified an urgent need for methodological rigour to strengthen the understanding of common mechanisms behind ageing and PD. Out of the wide range of overlapping mechanisms implicated in both ageing and PD studies, this consortium has prioritised protocols utilised for the investigation of senescence, inflammaging, omics profiling and mitochondrial dysfunction. Therefore, the standardisation of the *in vitro* techniques utilised to investigate the underlying pathways will not only reinforce individual studies within this field but also provide a robust framework to minimise variability and improve reproducibility.

While the current most preferred approach to studying PD-related changes, the iPSC cell reprogramming route, is well characterised, the benefits of other *in vitro* models conserving the epigenetic signature of the donor should be considered. This versatile tool is a method choice of a majority of the *in vitro* studies into neurodegeneration. With multiple techniques of induction of the ageing features into the iPSC-derived cells, further standardisation is necessary to increase the ability to compare findings across studies. On the contrary, the less characterised practice of obtaining cultured cells carrying the original ageing profile of the donor, have been shown to be a powerful tool for investigating age-related diseases. Despite the advantages of utilising the direct and semi-direct reprogramming approaches of generating cells and maintaining the biological background of the individual biopsy donor, robustness is necessary in the developing procedures. Uniform and efficient protocols will facilitate greater consistency and more accurate comparisons across studies from various institutions.

However, there are multiple outstanding questions future research should continue to explore to advance the ageing research in PD. One of the crucial challenges facing this field is distinguishing the age-specific effects from the PD-specific effects *in vitro*. This issue, especially vital in distinguishing mitochondrial characteristics and their age- and PD-specific changes will require further elucidation. Secondly, modelling disease progression in the context of ageing still requires refinement, as the current cellular models are unable to fully capture the gradual progression of the disease. Therefore, while the outlined practices may create a solid foundation for ageing and PD studies, avenues such as multi-cellular models, time-lapse investigations and incorporation of risk factors will be critical in the general standardisation across the field.

While the harmonisation of research practises is essential, its challenges should also be considered. For the research community to be able to draw meaningful conclusions achieved from standardised frameworks, the heterogeneity of research settings must be reviewed. Moreover, a key factor to evaluate during this process is the high level of complexity of PD and ageing, their various pathways of pathophysiology and the variability in their presentation across individuals. To overcome this, the process must be adaptable and constantly updated. Also, while great effort was implicated in the selection of methods for measuring the chosen parameters to include the most common laboratory equipment, the differences in technology and resource access may decelerate the standardisation process across regions. Therefore,

the PD-Age network emphasises the importance of international partnership and technological unification as indispensable means for establishing these common protocols.

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